

APPROPRIATE SELECTION OF AMBIENT DUST MONITORING PARAMETERS FOR INDIA: TESTING OF TOTAL VOLATILE MATTER OR BENZENE SOLUBLE ALTERNATIVES

C.B.S. Sengar, N. Bhattacharya and A.L. Aggarwal
Air Pollution Control Division,
National Environmental Engineering Research Institute, Nagpur, India

ABSTRACT

This paper reports the observations based on the analysis of suspended particulate matter (SPM) in Bombay city as a part of the NAQMN programme (National Air Quality Monitoring Network) covering three sampling sites viz: Bandra (residential), Kalbadevi (commercial) and Parel (industrial). SPM samples were collected with Hi-vol sampler over a period of 24-hrs and quantified gravimetrically. They were further analyzed for Benzene Soluble Fractions (BSF) with Volatile Organic Matter (TVM). The levels of total BSF in Bombay were comparable with those of cosmopolitan cities like Calcutta and Delhi. The statistical significance status of correlation between BSF and total SPM was found best in the rainy season. This study highlighted that the rise in SPM values is not accompanied by the proportional rise in BSF and TVM and hence, despite large variations in SPM data, these parameters remain consistent. Less variability in BSF and TVM confirmed that these parameters are not affected by background dust which is the main cause of high fluctuations in SPM values.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Air pollution in urban areas arises from a multitude of sources. The importance of a particular type of source and thereby, the choice of an appropriate monitoring parameter is, to a certain extent, dependent on the location and climate. Large scale monitoring of pollutants in the world

has been limited to using concentration of sulphur dioxide and SPM in urban environments. For the determination of SPM, the method recommended by authorities concerned with air pollution management is based on Hi-Vol sampling. The annual average SPM levels recorded through this technique under the Global Environment Monitoring (GEM) Programme covering 136 sites varied in the range of 24-547 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cu.m}$. Out of the total of 303 points of data, 55 were above 200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cu.m}$. and three cities: Calcutta, Delhi and Tehran – accounted for the 40 points above 300 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cu.m}$. (WHO, 1984). These studies confirm the high variations in world wide SPM data which is also true in the case of Indian cities. In major Indian urban centres, the variability in SPM values is so large that SD is even higher than prescribed international or national standards primarily due to non-anthropogenic factors (background).

TVM and BSF of atmospheric dust are concentrated in smaller size smoke dust/fumes. Size of these particles is very small ($< 10 \mu\text{m}$) (Faith, 1985), which also represent the inhalable fraction of dust. This portion of dust is mostly released from all combustion processes which incidentally is also the prime source of energy for all domestic or commercial activities including vehicular transport. Observations represented here are based on analysis of Bombay SPM samples, collected under continued NAQMN study since 1978 ((NAQMN, 1978-86). Bombay is one of the largest industrialized cities in India having minimum background dust being on seashore, away from dry climatic

zones of central and northern Indian regions which come under the influence of dust and storm.

2.0 SAMPLING SITES AND TECHNIQUES

Bombay is a densely populated city located on the west coast with heavy industrial and commercial activities. The city has more than 6000 industrial units (textile, chemical and engineering) of various sizes, besides three refineries, a fertilizer complex and a thermal power plant. Three sampling sites viz: Bandra, Kalbadevi and Parel were selected. Bandra is a purely residential area, while Kalbadevi represents commercial and Parel is an industrial and mixed use area. SPM samples were collected with a Hi-Vol sampler operated at an average flow rate of 1.5 cu.m./min over a period of 24 hours. Suspended particulate matter thus collected was quantified gravimetrically on a pre-weighted glass fibre filter paper and results were expressed in $\mu\text{g}/\text{cu.m.}$ of air.

3.0 ANALYTICAL TECHNIQUE

Total of 100 SPM samples were analyzed for BSF and TVM from selected filter papers collected for the whole year for three stations. Although many solvents can be used for the extraction of solubles but benzene has been found better (Tabor et al., 1961) and was preferred because of its ability to extract most of the carcinogenic organic compounds. Twenty circles of 1.0 cm diameter were cut from an exposed filter paper, and transferred into a paper thimble which is finally inserted into the extraction chamber of a Soxhlet apparatus. The extraction chamber was then filled with 150 ml benzene and attached with the fluxing apparatus having a condenser and was heated on a heating mantle. Adequate precautions were taken so that the digestion temperature did not exceed the boiling point of benzene. The digestion cycles, which required about 7 hrs., extracted 95-100 per cent of benzene solubles. Extracted matter was evaporated in a pre-weighted 100 ml beaker to dryness at room temperature and re-weighted for determining BSF. For quantifying TVM, 20 circles were again punched from the same exposed filter paper and were muffled at 550°C in

a pre-weighted porcelain crucible for 6 hrs. and finally cooled in a desiccator and re-weighted (APHA, 1985). The TVM present in samples was determined gravimetrically.

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Annual mean values for BSF and TVM for different areas are given in Table 1 and 2 respectively. Figure 1 shows the monthly variation of SPM, BSF and TVM in different areas. Levels of TVM varied between 50 to 170 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cu.m.}$ depending upon the type of the season and area. Maximum concentrations (170 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cu.m.}$) was observed in the industrial area where fuel oil or coal is the main industrial fuel. Minimum concentration was observed for the residential area (50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cu.m.}$) because of major use of kerosene and LPG as the source of domestic energy. Similar trends were observed for BSF, although levels of BSF were comparatively less in all the zones (Fig. 1). Annual mean of BSF in Bombay varied between 47 and 82 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cu.m.}$ depending upon the activity and fuel used in three areas (Table 1). In 144 cities of USA, BSF constituted only 8.2% (NAQMN, 1978-86) of the total

Table 1
Annual BSF Levels ($\mu\text{g}/\text{cu.m.}$) in Bombay

Zones	Observations	Annual BSF Levels ($\mu\text{g}/\text{cu.m.}$)			
		Avg.	SD	Min.	Max.
Industrial	30	82.36	24.00	40.00	126.37
Commercial	32	63.03	12.67	42.42	90.50
Residential	31	47.78	12.65	21.80	69.43

Table 2
Annual TVM Levels ($\mu\text{g}/\text{cu.m.}$) in Bombay

Zones	Observations	Annual TVM Levels ($\mu\text{g}/\text{cu.m.}$)			
		Avg.	SD	Min.	Max.
Industrial	30	128.20	35.01	56.50	188.25
Commercial	32	97.78	21.04	60.90	139.50
Residential	31	72.92	17.51	48.00	112.20

Table 3
Annual Mean Values of SPM ($\mu\text{g}/\text{cu.m}$) and Their 95th Percentile
In Different Areas of Major Cities

Year City	Industrial SPM			Commercial SPM			Residential SPM		
	Avg.	SD	Percentile	Avg.	SD	Percentile	Avg.	SD	Percentile
Year-1984									
Bombay	240	103	409	156	94	311	235	121	392
Calcutta	475	235	813	413	243	713	289	210	659
Delhi	498	251	946	482	261	881	308	230	553
Kanpur	359	136	600	366	185	600	240	122	437
Jaipur	297	172	575	448	270	718	240	115	426
Year-1985									
Bombay	223	76	330	175	91	317	289	117	470
Calcutta	404	201	796	374	168	626	277	161	500
Delhi	488	247	878	439	233	767	294	160	526
Kanpur	320	148	553	373	197	704	215	124	431
Jaipur	290	172	604	430	172	705	277	184	545

SPM and if the same ratio of BSF to total dust is applied, then the SPM concentration obtained may vary between 573 and 1000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cu.m}$. This range of SPM levels can not be permitted under USA or any other country's standard including India. In India, Central Board for Prevention and Control of Water Pollution (CBPCWP) has recommended SPM concentration of 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cu.m}$ (95th percentile values) for industrial and mixed use areas. In Bombay, which could be classified under industrial and mixed use areas, the observed high-

est mean annual SPM concentration of the same period did not exceed even 289 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cu.m}$. which fall within the acceptable levels as per Indian standards. It may be because of low background concentration than other inland Indian cities of central and northern regions (Table 3). In comparison to 8.2% BSF in SPM in USA cities, these fractions in our studies ranged between 12 and 45% (Figure 2) depending upon season and area. It is observed that BSF percentages in SPM are slightly increased during the rainy season because

Table 4
BSF Content in SPM of Some Major Indian Cities

Sr. No.	Stations	BSF $\mu\text{g}/\text{cu.m}$	% BSF in SPM
1.	Calcutta	87.0	16.0
2.	Delhi	93.0	13.0
3.	Hyderabad	32.0	16.0
4.	Kanpur	37.0	16.0
5.	Nagpur	46.0	12.0
6.	Jaipur	25.0	07.0
7.	Bombay	64.0	28.0

Table 5
Seasonal Correlation Coefficient Between BSF and SPM in Bombay

Season	Industrial	Commercial	Residential
Winter (Nov-Feb)	-0.0756	0.2646	-0.7291*
Summer (March-June)	0.5487*	0.3242	0.7201*
Rainy (July-Oct)	0.9600*	0.7900*	0.2122

* Shows the significance of correlation at 5% level

of suppression of background dust under rain/washout influence. Sharma et al. (Sharma, 1983) have also reported the highest percentages of BSF in SPM during the rainy season in Kanpur city. In the industrial area, it is relatively less in the rainy season which may be due to less industrial activity in that area. Highest percentage of BSF is observed in the commercial area which may be due to higher emissions from automobile activity in the commercial sector during that particular time. In other Indian cities, such percentages of BSF were encountered between 7.2 and 16% and the lowest was recorded in Jaipur city (Thakre and Sharma, 1983). These results are summarized in Table 4. In Jaipur, low percentage of BSF may be because of strong background sources as the city is located in the semi arid zone of Rajasthan. Highly industrialized and commercially active cities like Calcutta, Hyderabad and Kanpur recorded a comparatively higher percentage of BSF but still much lower than Bombay values. The levels of BSF in Bombay in terms of $\mu\text{g}/\text{cu. m.}$ could be compared with that of other cosmopolitan cities like Calcutta and Delhi having large vehicular sources. The statistical significance status of correlations between BSF and SPM (Table 5 & 6) as well as TVM and SPM was found best in the rainy season again because of low background concentration during this season.

Table 6

Seasonal Correlation Coefficient Between TVM and SPM in Bombay

Season	Industrial	Commercial	Residential
Winter (Nov-Feb)	0.8812*	-0.2290	-0.1764
Summer (March-June)	0.8585*	0.9172*	-0.2133
Rainy (July-Oct)	0.9842*	0.9973*	0.2088

* Shows the significance of correlation at 5% level

The TVM of the unburnt portion is primarily emitted during combustion of fuels, which may also include BSF but not in excessive quantities,

whereas, the major source for BSF is automobile and domestic fuel burning (wood, coal residues and coal). Hence, in the case of TVM, the ratio of TVM to dust is more than that of BSF to dust. The annual ratio between TVM and BSF remains unchanged (Table 7) which again shows the small variability in these parameters.

Table 7

Seasonal Ratio of TVM to BSF in SPM of Bombay

	Industrial	Commercial	Residential
Winter	1.5	1.6	1.6
Summer	1.7	1.7	1.7
Rainy	1.5	1.3	1.5
Annual	1.5	1.5	1.6

In USA and other western countries, the earlier adopted method of fixing ambient standards is under criticism because of two major factors. Firstly, standards should be based on inhalable ($< 10\mu\text{m}$) particles and should be representative of the total cumulative exposure of different categories of receptors. The present standards fixed in India serve little purpose because of large background dust with unpredictable variability due to large-scale differences in seasonal, geographical as well as micro-meteorological conditions. The size of such background dust of non-anthropogenic nature is also not inhalable and primarily consists of inert material. Since BSF and TVM represent inhalable particle size dust and have comparatively higher consistency without being affected by background dust, hence, these parameters will be more reliable than SPM to represent the local pollution status from public health point of view. Ambient standards, based on such parameters, will reduce the ambiguity associated with SPM variations with Indian urban centres because of their large background dust. These aspects are being further investigated at NEERI, Nagpur and SPM analysis from 10 major Indian urban centres is being subjected to detailed chemical characterization and comprehensive report after publication and may ultimately form the primary basis of criteria development for fixing ambient air SPM levels for the Indian Subcontinent.

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